

On the Origin and Nature of Dark Energy, Dark Matter and the Expansion of the Universe

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Abstract

This paper postulates that Dark Energy and Dark Matter are manifestations of gravitational energy arising from the expansion of the Universe and identifies the source of this energy as the kinetic energy of the baryonic matter present at Big Bang.

Keywords - Dark Energy, Dark Matter, Big Bang, Cosmology, Universe, Expansion

1 Introduction

Various analyses of the rotating velocities of spiral galaxies, and the non-Keplerian motion observed in the stellar masses rotating around the cores of these galaxies have led the scientific community to propose and widely accept 'dark matter' (herein after, DM) as the component leading to this counter-intuitive motion. DM is thought to be contained in a 'halo' around the galactic core, and provides the missing mass necessary to prevent the visible stellar masses from flying off at a tangent. This DM is further thought to be non-interacting with electromagnetic radiation, but interacts with gravitational fields.

Similarly, the observed accelerating expansion of the Universe has led the scientific community to equally propose and widely accept 'dark energy' (herein after, DE) as the component providing the energy required for this expansion. This DE, like DM, is also thought to be non-interacting with electromagnetic radiation, but interacts with gravitational fields.

These novel explanations have served the prevailing cosmological models very well, however questions into the nature of DM and DE still abound because experimental inquiries have so far yielded no clues.

But was there a need in the first place to propose these components and ascribe to them mythical properties? In this paper I will show that the answer is negative, that all that is needed is a closer look at the results of the kinematics of bodies accelerating through the fabric of space-time.

2 The Cosmological Principle

The Cosmological Principle states that on the large-scale, the structure of the Universe is homogeneous and isotropic. Experimental observations (Lahav, 1999) have largely supported this principle, with Scrimgeour et al. (2012) setting the lower limit for statistical homogeneity at 250 million light-years. The large-scale structure of the Universe is therefore a space-time lattice (albeit an expanding one) with a homogeneous and isotropic distribution of matter. Matter is held in place in this ever-expanding lattice by gravity which acts on all matter and across the Universe following Mach's Principle.

What causes this expansion of the Universe and what prevents the Universe from collapsing back into itself? The answer is simple: the overall outward expansion started at Big Bang. The Big Bang event provided the momentum to keep the Universe in a state of expansion ever since, the force of expansion being greater than the attractive force of gravitation. We shall now use this simple idea to explain the source and nature of DM and DE.

3 Explanation for Dark Energy and Dark Matter

I now make the following postulate: the expansion of the Universe which started at Big Bang causes an increase in inertial/gravitational masses of individual receding bodies and this increase manifests itself as gravitational energy. This gravitational energy is what is DE, and DM when expressed in terms of mass. DE and DM are therefore manifestations of the kinetic energy imparted on baryonic matter at Big Bang, this kinetic energy having been greater than the attractive gravitational energy of the total baryonic matter for the expansion to have occurred.

3.1 Dark Energy

We will make use of a thought-experiment. In addition, we will consider three fundamental principles as necessary for the explanation: the Cosmological Principle, the Equivalence Principle, The Relativity of Time and the Law of Conservation of Momentum.

Consider a massive observer body (a body, upon which a fixed frame of reference is established, containing an observer) and a test particle, for instance a neutrino, at a finite but increasing distance from the observer body due to the expansion of the Universe.

Experimental results e.g. Hubble (1929) have shown that the Universe is expanding, and at an accelerated pace. Therefore as the distance between the observer body and the receding test particle increases, the geometry of spacetime the test particle traverses increasingly becomes flat. Two things happen:

1. The force of gravity experienced by the test particle continually decreases, and for the Law of Conservation of Momentum to be maintained, the receding test particle obtains an equivalent boost in velocity as it traverses its outward-bound geodesic, and

2. Looking at the scenario in terms of time, the particle experiences time-dilation (from the principle of Relativity of Time, a clock runs slower with increasing relative speeds or with strengthening gravitational fields).

As a result of the increasing velocity and hence increasing kinetic energy, the receding test particle obtains an equivalent increase in inertial mass from Einstein's mass-energy relation

$$E = mc^2 \quad (1)$$

or

$$m = \frac{E}{c^2} \quad (2)$$

This increase in inertial mass implies an increase in gravitational mass from the Equivalence Principle and hence an increase in gravitational energy.

The so-called DE is thus nothing more than the resultant kinetic energy that was imparted on all baryonic matter at Big Bang and is responsible for the observed accelerated recession of bodies in the Universe. This kinetic energy in turn is manifested as gravitational energy homogeneously spread in the Universe.

Is the recession a physical reality? An increase in gravitational energy with increasing distance cancels out any net change in the gravitational potential between the observer body and the test particle, and this counter-intuitively implies no change in displacement. The dimming of light from standard candles with the passage of time implies increasing displacement, however it can also imply a strengthening gravitational field such that the luminosity continually decreases up to zero when a black hole forms (in our example of a receding test particle, the mass of the test particle approaches infinity as it moves with velocities closer to the speed of light. At these velocities the gravitational field generated compresses the generated mass into a black hole).

3.2 Dark Matter

Let us consider a disc galaxy, and assume that the distribution of stellar mass-energy in the galaxy is homogeneous. The whole galaxy therefore acts as a contiguous body, and all component stars will rotate about the galactic axis with the same angular velocity.

The galaxy is prevented from collapsing into itself by the outward expansion of the galaxy as a result of the overall expansion of the Universe and the centripetal force arising from its rotation. If the galaxy were to stop rotating, the stellar masses would collapse into its centre. It can be said therefore that the gravitational force in each mass is balanced to a certain extent by the centripetal force due to the masses rotating about the centre and the Universal 'force' of expansion the source of which we have described in the preceding sections. Because the galaxy is also expanding at an accelerating rate, this causes an increase in velocity and thus an increase in inertial mass and hence gravitational mass. It can be deduced therefore that the unexplained DM is actually gravitational mass due to the expanding galaxy.

The so-called DM is thus nothing more than the mass equivalent of the resultant kinetic energy that was imparted on all baryonic matter at Big Bang and is responsible for the observed accelerated recession of bodies in the Universe.

4 Conclusion

DM and DE are the resultant kinetic energy that was imparted on all baryonic matter at Big Bang and which is responsible for the observed accelerated recession of bodies in the Universe.

It is postulated that the DM content of the Universe is a measure of its DE content, and the two are related by Einstein's Mass-Energy Equivalence equation.

References

1. Einstein, A. (1911). On the Influence of Gravitation on the Propagation of Light. In *Annalen der Physik*, Vol. 35, pp.898-908
2. Lahav, O. (1999). *Observational Tests for the Cosmological Principle and World Models*. Cambridge: Isaac Newton Institute
3. Scrimgeour et al. (2012). *The Wiggle Z Dark Energy Survey: the transition to large-scale cosmic homogeneity*. Retrieved from arXiv.org